

Turbine Tone Noise Prediction in High Speed Turbines Using a Linearized CFD Solver: Comparison with Measurements

José R. Fernández Aparicio¹ and Adolfo Serrano González²
ITP Aero, Francisca Delgado, n°9, 28018 Alcobendas, Spain

Gadea García Cuevas³
Centro de Tecnologías Aeronáuticas (CTA), Parque Tecnológico de Bizkaia, Edificio 303, 48170 Zamudio, Spain

The noise generation in HST is investigated through numerical predictions and rig testing. Experimental vehicles consist of two state-of-the-art rigs representative of forward and rear part of a HST. Both rigs are tested in the Centro de Tecnologías Aeronáuticas (CTA) facility (Bilbao, Spain). The comparison with numerical predictions includes multi-stage effects, acoustic coupling and optimized vane shape, as well as the noise generation from a low count, low aspect ratio vane.

I. Nomenclature

B	=	Number of Blades
CFD	=	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CTA	=	Centro de Tecnologías Aeronáuticas
f	=	Frequency
GPU	=	Graphics Processing Unit
i	=	Complex number $\sqrt{-1}$
ITP	=	Industria de Turbo Propulsores
k	=	Scatter index
LPT	=	Low Pressure Turbine
HST	=	High Speed Turbine
m	=	Circumferential Wave Number or Spinning Mode
MPI	=	Message Passing Interface
$\text{Mu}^2\text{s}^2\text{T}$	=	Multirow Unsteady Unstructured Specific Solver for Turbomachinery
PWL	=	Sound Power Level
RANS	=	Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes
r	=	Radial Position
U	=	Flow Vector or Eigenfunction
v	=	Flow Velocity
V	=	Number of Vanes
ω	=	Excitation Frequency

II. Introduction

Turbine noise is an important source to the overall perceived aircraft levels. Landing is the condition in which this component is typically more prominent related to the other engine and airframe sources. Its contribution is commonly reduced by a smart selection of rotating and stationary parts through the different stages together with the use of acoustic treatment in the hot nozzle [1]. With the increasing demand for delivering quieter but at the same time greener engines, Industry is looking for alternatives for the state of the art reduction practices aimed to deliver a better

¹ Associate Technical Fellow in Aeroacoustics.

² Technical Fellow in Aeroacoustics.

³ Aeroacoustic Test Manager.

product. This is particularly relevant for the UltraFan® family of engines in which the High Speed Turbine (HST) makes more noise in comparison with the equivalent Direct Drive Low Speed Turbines (LPTs) [2].

The look for alternatives for optimizing turbine noise requires the use of high fidelity prediction methods. Turbine tones in particular can be estimated using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Computational Aero Acoustics (CAA), with demonstrated increased prediction capability over semi-analytical methods [3][4][9]. This increase confidence in the prediction makes feasible the use of less conservative design rules, giving a better multi-disciplinary product. Numerical tools allows the investigation and development of novel technologies for reducing noise such as Acoustic Coupling (AC), Optimized Vane Shape (OVS) or the combination of both [6][22].

Whereas the use of Euler fluid models provides good accuracy for fan tonal noise [7], the use of at least Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) method becomes necessary for turbines due to the role of the viscous effects in the turbine tone noise generation [8].

The capability for predicting tone noise in LPTs has been already assessed with the comparison of measurements from various rigs and engines [6][9]. However, these conclusions might not be straight applicable for HST since the design space and noise generation mechanisms are generally not the same, at least not all of them. The purpose of this work is continuing the work initiated in [6][9] for LPTs and extend the analysis to the HST design space. This will be done comparing numerical predictions with measurements from two cold flow rigs, representative of a front a rear part multi-stage HST. The work starts describing the numerical methodology emphasizing the upgrades from the described for LPTs [6]. This is continued with the description of the facility in which noise measurements have been taken. Then the two Test Cases are presented, describing vehicles, working conditions and predicted vs measured noise comparisons from which conclusions are derived.

III. Codes and Methodology

Numerical predictions will be done with Mu²s²T, that is an in-house, second order accurate CFD solver with common characteristics from those used in Industry for Aerodynamics, Aeroelasticity and Aeroacoustics, and with demonstrated capability over the years [6][11][12][13][14]. Hybrid unstructured grids based to discretize the spatial domain and an edge data structure to compute the fluxes. Steady RANS, Unsteady RANS (URANS) in time domain, Linearized RANS (LRANS) in frequency domain are the Mu²s²T capabilities of interest for Aeroacoustics computations. Other characteristics of interest are: Time-marching technique with an explicit five-stage Runge-Kutta, Multigrid [11] to accelerate convergence, Message Passing Interface (MPI) and able to run in Graphic Processing Units (GPUs) [10]. Mu²s²T is currently used for the design of ITP Aero products.

LRANS method is the method used here for deriving noise predictions. It has 3D Unsteady Non-Reflecting Boundary Conditions (3DUNRBC) at every inlet and outlet of each computational domain. Formulation is based on radial mode decomposition for viscous and radially varying swirling flows [15]. Noise prediction procedure is based on extracting perturbations from the steady or main flow computation and pursue them until the turbine exit, as detailed in Fernandez Aparicio [12][13]. Mu²s²T has the capability of running in a multi-stage environment for both steady and linearized unsteady computations retaining multiple acoustic reflections between rows [23]. 3DUNRBC and Aeroacoustic Analysis for deriving sound levels are performed using RECKONER, an in-house set of tools for Pre and post-processing unsteady flows. RECKONER performs Fourier decomposition for each radius, finds fundamental solutions by resolving the eigen-value problems and finally it has two wave-splitting techniques for estimating the quasi-vorticity and quasi-acoustic field at given axial position [16].

IV. Facility Description and Noise Instrumentation

Noise measurements presented here have been acquired in the Centro de Tecnologías Aeronáicas (CTA) facility sited in Bilbao, Spain. It is an open circuit transonic wind tunnel, with continuous mass flow up to 20 kg/s, able to measure several stages of a scaled turbine powering a large thrust turbofan engine, under realistic Reynolds and Mach Numbers. More information on the facility characteristics and how it operates can be found in Vazquez et al. [17].

Noise measurements are acquired immediately downstream the turbine section as schematically shown in Figure 1, 'In-duct' taken and by means of a continuous rotating device called Noise Measurement Module (NMM). Two arrays of 24 and 22 transducers are located in two circumferential positions and non-uniform placed in axial direction. This is for maximizing the outcomes from the Radial Mode Decomposition (RMD) [5]. Those transducers are Kulite XT-190M 5psi range and are flush mounted in the outer wall. An acoustic liner downstream the NMM aims to isolate turbine sources from those coming from the facility. Besides the rotating transducers, additional sets of non-rotating microphones are located at different locations aimed to support the RMD process [18] and to check facility sources.

Noise is acquired at steady state conditions and with a continuous NMM rotation of almost 360 degrees in about five minutes. Data is recorded with two PXIs (models 1045 and 1006), with seven analogic acquisition cards (model PXI-4472), with 8 channel each. Frequency sampling rate is 51200 Hz. More details of the noise acquisition system and data reduction procedure can be found in Serrano et al. [5][18].

Figure 1 Schematic view of the Noise Measurement Module (NMM)

Figure 2 VT3 rig assembly with the two rotor rows.

V. Test Case 1 1: 1.5 Stage Rig of HST Front Part

A. Vehicle and Test Description

VT3 is one and a half stage representative of the forward part of UltraFan® IP Turbine. It has a first blade row (said rotor0) followed by a first Nozzle Guide Vane (NGV) with a low count and low aspect ratio, then another rotor and NGV which number-off is 3 times the NGV1 number-off. The Blade row count is such that the interaction between NGV1 and Blade1 is cut-on for certain harmonics of the perturbations coming from NGV1. The interaction between Blade 1 and NGV2 is cut-on for the first harmonic of the perturbations coming from these rows. Figure 2 shows a picture of the rig assembly with the two rotor rows on it and Figure 3 shows schematically the rig lay-out.

Figure 3 VT3 schematic view

The number-off relation between vanes 1 and 2 allows the clocking phenomenon investigation in HST. In particular, the third harmonic of the perturbations coming from vane 1 interacting with rotor 1 can clock with the noise generated by the interaction of rotor 1 and vane 2. This was taken into account in the test scheduling with a hardware design that allows the measurement of 8 clocking positions between the two vanes. The positioning system is located in vane 2, which can be placed at equidistant circumferential positions over one pitch with steps of 12.5% of its pitch.

Three working lines representative of the rig placed in an engine have been tested, corresponding different loadings in the rows, resulting in an overall of 24 working conditions. The range in shaft speed is 40-100% taking as reference the reduced shaft speed of the cruise condition.

Regarding noise measurements procedure, for a given stabilized condition, the NMM completes almost 360° with a constant rotating velocity. In this test, it takes 5 minutes to complete one rotation, having a second acquisition when the NMM rotates back to the initial position. In this case, a faster rotation of 2.5 minutes is used for assessing the stability of each condition. Prior to the noise campaign, an aerodynamic campaign was performed to characterize the rig in terms of aerodynamics (turbine performance, stator wakes). The noise measurements were taken in absence of any aerodynamic instrumentation such rakes or aerodynamic probes between the turbine rig and the NMM.

B. Numerical Model

The turbine tones to be simulated are labelled as 1LPT1-X-Y, where X is 1 or 2 depending if the interaction is originally initiated between V1-B1 (1LPT1-1) or B1-V2 (1LPT1-2). Y is used to represent different harmonics of vane 1 perturbations interacting with rotor 1. Spinning modes generated follow Tyler&Sofrin rule [20], using in this work the nomenclature B1-xVX, being x any integer.

Figure 4 VT3 Geometry and Computational Domain

Figure 4 shows the airfoils geometry and computational domain used for the simulation. Rotor0 noise is not interesting for the purpose of the work and it is not included in the simulation. Although not seen in this figure, but present in the installation and included in the simulations, there is a duct where noise is propagated until the NMM.

The simulation is performed in two steps: 1) Stator 1 – Rotor 1- Stator 2 interaction considering multiple reflections between Rotor 1 and Stator 2; 2) Transmission of acoustic sources through the duct existing between the turbine and the NMM. Due to the duct geometry, it is not included in the multi-row simulation in order to reduce the size of the multi-row simulation, given that the duct does not play a major role in the multiple reflections process occurring between rows. Therefore, the importance of the reflections originated in the duct is assumed low.

A set of aerodynamic and acoustic grids is generated to perform the simulations. The aerodynamic grids are used to extract the mechanisms that generate noise, which are the wakes and potential fields of the rows. These aerodynamic grids are hybrid, consisting of a structured region in the boundary layer to properly solve the profile losses ($y^+ < 1$), a structured wake grid at the trailing edge region and an unstructured grid in the inviscid area. Spanwise are structured with 129 planes with stretching near the hub and tip. The acoustics grids are suitable for propagating the perturbations that generate noise and they are dimensioned taking into account the smallest wavelength considering all the cut-on radial modes of interest in each row. The number of radial planes in these acoustic grids is modified to 130, as well as the stretching near the endwalls, to prioritize the radial modes resolution spanwise. Table 1 shows the grid size of the aerodynamic and acoustic grids used in the simulations. The acoustic grids are only used for Rotor 1 and NGV2, as the NGV1 is only used to extract the perturbations coming from this row. Two acoustic grids are used depending on the mode that is propagated in order to reduce the computational resources needed.

SIZE (10⁶ Nodes)	NGV1	Rotor 1	NGV 2
Aerodynamic grid	8.2	5.0	5.2
Acoustic grid 1	-	3.8	5.5
Acoustic grid 2	-	1.4	1.5

Table 1. Test Case 1: Grid size for each row.

The turbulence model used in the simulations is Baldwin-Lomax [24]. Although this model is recommended for aeroacoustics simulations [6], certain limitations have been observed for high order harmonics of the vane 1 wake when compared with the wake measurements. For this reason, the results coming from other turbulent models such as Wilcox $k-\omega$ [25] are also accounted in the simulations.

The source mechanisms responsible of generating tone noise at the first Blade Passing Frequency (BPF) are:

- First five wake and potential field harmonics of vane 1 interacting with downstream blade 1
- First leading edge potential field harmonic of blade 1 interacting with upstream vane 1
- First wake and potential field harmonic of blade 1 interacting with downstream vane 2
- First leading edge potential field harmonic of blade 1 interacting with upstream vane 1

C. Results

One of the main interests in this rig is the noise generated in the vane 1 due to its low aspect ratio and number-off. Several harmonics of the wake of this vane can generate noise by interaction with the downstream rows, rotor 1 and vane 2. A RANS simulation of this row with the recommended turbulence model is used to predict wake amplitude and phase. For a given nominal landing representative working condition, **Figure 5** and **Figure 6** show the comparison of the first four harmonics at the outlet of the vane 1 domain with the measured wake at the same axial position. Numerical predictions capability is comparable with that found for LPTs [6].

Figure 5 First (left) and second (right) wake harmonic content for VT3 NGV1: (a) and (b) amplitude and phase for first wake harmonic; (c) and (d) amplitude and phase for second wake harmonic.

Figure 6 Third (left) and Fourth (right) wake harmonic content for VT3 NGV1: (a) and (b) amplitude and phase for third wake harmonic; (c) and (d) amplitude and phase for fourth wake harmonic.

Three working conditions are simulated and compared with measurements: nominal Approach working condition (TP302), Approach with increased loading (TP404) and Approach with increased shaft speed (TP305).

All the mechanisms contributing to the noise generation at 1BPF are simulated. Some of these mechanisms are shown in Figure 7. The first harmonic of vane 1 wake can generate two modes that are cut-on (Figure 7a). Mode 1B1-1V1-V2 is also generated by the interaction of the fourth harmonic (Figure 7b), thus these mechanisms are able to be clocked. Total energy associated to this mode depends on the relative position between vane 1 and vane 2 as argued in Vazquez et al [19]. Figure 7c and d shows the acoustic modes that can be generated by the interaction of the 2nd and 5th harmonic with rotor 1 and vane 2. These two mechanisms are correlated as well and resulting energy will depend on the clocking position.

Figure 7 Mechanisms accounted in the VT3 NGV1 noise related sources

Additionally to the mechanisms shown in Figure 7, there are other sources that can contribute to generate noise at those modes and that need to be taken into account when comparing with measurements and assessing the clocking sensitivity.

Figure 8 shows the uncorrelated acoustic energy coming from the first five wake harmonics simulated in comparison with measurements for the nominal Approach condition (TP302). An agreement is observed regarding the relative contribution between harmonics and prediction capability found, in alignment with that obtained in LPTs [20].

Figure 9 shows the same analysis done for the other two conditions with higher loading (TP404) and higher shaft speed (TP305), where the prediction from 3rd to 5th harmonic is worsened for the latter.

Figure 8 VT3 Predicted and measured NGV1 wake harmonic uncorrelated noise for the nominal Approach TP302

Figure 9 VT3 Predicted and measured NGV1 wake harmonic uncorrelated noise for the Approach with increased loading (TP404, left) and increased speed (TP305, right)

Figure 10 shows the clocking sensitivity predicted and measured for the two modes marked in Figure 7 (1B1-1V1-1V2 and 1B1-2V1-1V2) and another mode generated by the third harmonic of vane 1 (1B1-3V1-1V2). The sum of these three modes is also represented in the plot. As concluded from Figure 8 and Figure 9, the mean noise level or uncorrelated is well captured in the simulation, except for mode 1B1-3V1-1V2 where an over-prediction is observed. The optimum position for noise is in agreement with the measurements with a mean deviation of 15%, that is consistent with the conclusions obtained in LPTs [6][9][22]. The clocking sensitivity is also well explained with the simulations performed, confirming that the mechanisms considered are those that play a major role in the noise generation of these modes.

Figure 10 VT3 Predicted (left) and measured (right) clocking sensitivity for the nominal Approach TP302

Figure 11 VT3 Predicted and measured clocking sensitivity for the nominal Approach TP302 given for 1B1-2V1-1V2 mode (left) and 1B1-1V1-1V2 mode (right)

Figure 11 shows, for the same nominal Approach (TP302), the analysis of radial content for 1B1-1V1-1V2 (left), and 1B1-2V1-1V2 (right). Regarding mode 1B1-1V1-1V2, the measurement is clearly dominated by the first radial mode, with very low contribution of the second and radial mode. On the contrary, the numerical predicted radial content gives similar importance to the first and second radial mode. The situation is different for mode 1B1-2V1-1V2, where the first radial mode dominates the measurement whereas the simulation shows the second radial mode as dominant. There is not a big impact in the circumferential mode sensitivity, where there is good agreement between measurement and simulation; however, the problems to capture the radial mode content could lead to mis-predictions when including other elements in the noise propagation inside the engine such as acoustically treated nozzles or in the outside radiation of these modes. Difficulties in capturing the radial modal content is not specific of HST and were also observed in LPTs [6].

VI. Test Cases 2&3: 1.5 Stage Rigs of HST Rear Part

D. Vehicles and Test Description

VT4-1 is one and a half stage representative of a rear part of UltraFan® IP Turbine. It has two NGV rows with the same count in order to understand the AC effects in High Speed Turbines. The Blade row count is such the interaction between NGV and Blade is cut-on at Approach representative working conditions. VT4-3 is a reblading of VT4-1 in which the second NGV row is re-designed including OVS. Figure 12 shows a picture of the rig assembly and Figure 13 shows schematically the Lay-Outs for these two builds.

Noise measurements were taken along working conditions with row aerodynamics representative of Approach in an engine. The shaft speed range tested goes from 50% to 75% the design speed and the loading is modified to have different row aerodynamics, i.e. front, mid or rear part of the turbine in the engine. For a given stabilized condition, the NMM completes almost 360° with a constant rotating velocity of 5 minutes. A second acquisition were performed in 2.5 minutes for assessing the stability of each condition. An overall of 32 test points corresponding to five working lines were measured on each session. The first NGV rows does have a tangential positioning system allowing the measurements of 8 equidistant clocking positions. Each of them was dedicated for one of the clocking positions of VT4-1 and VT4-3, having an overall of eighteen noise sessions including a repeatability session for each of the two rigs. Noise measurements were taken in absence of any aerodynamic instrumentation such as rakes or aerodynamic probes between the turbine rig and the NMM. Besides the noise sessions, an aerodynamic campaign was performed in order to characterize the stator wakes and the flow in the NMM in order to perform the modal decomposition.

Figure 12 VT4-1 rig assembly

Figure 13 VT4-1 (left) and VT4-3 (right) Schematic Lay-Out

E. Numerical Model

Blade and NGV counts in both VT4-1 and VT4-3 is such that there is a unique dominant interaction into the first Blade Passing Frequency (BPF) at the Landing representative working conditions of interest. Consequently, numerical grids are dimensioned to capture this dominant interaction. Source mechanisms responsible for the generation of noise are (i) First NGV wake and potential harmonic interacting with downstream blade row (ii) Blade row Leading Edge first potential harmonic interacting with upstream NGV row (iii) First Blade wake and potential harmonic interacting with downstream NGV row and (iv) Second NGV row potential field interacting with upstream blade row. A hierarchy of grids is constructed for each row depending on the simulation performed: (i) aerodynamic grid for steady or main flow estimation (ii) high density grid for estimating the generation of noise (iii) lower density grid for estimating multiple reflections between rows of the sources generated. AC sensitivity is estimated as the correlated sum of these individual mechanisms that are dependent on the relative position between NGV rows. Figure 14 shows the computational domain. Table 2 shows the resulting aerodynamic and acoustic grid sizes. Two acoustic grids are used in NGV2 depending on the mode that is propagated with the objective of reducing the computational resources needed.

SIZE (10 ⁶ Nodes)	NGV 1	Rotor 1	NGV 2
Aero grid	1.9	1.7	2.4
Acoustic grid 1	1.0	2.7	3.7
Acoustic grid 2	-	-	1.1

Table 2. Test Case 2&3: Grid size for each row.

Figure 14. Computational domain used in rig VT4-1.

F. Results

The dominant mechanisms of noise generation are the wakes coming from the first vane and from the first rotor, interacting with the downstream rows. Therefore, the evaluation of the numerical capability to predict these perturbations is of capital interest to conclude regarding the noise prediction capability. Figure 15 shows the amplitude and phase of the first harmonic of the wake coming from NGV2 for two Approach representative working conditions. Left plots (a and b) shows the case with zero flow incidence, whereas the plots on the right (c and d) represents a condition with flow incidence. Numerical predictions (black lines) are compared with measured results from five-hole pneumatic probes. Amplitude level, shape and wake alignment (phase) is captured with similar confidence as in previous experiments with LPTs [6][22]. The relative amplitude increase when introducing the flow incidence is in consistency with measurements although both amplitude shape and alignment (phase) is more difficult to capture.

Figure 15 Wake harmonic intensity for the second NGV row: (a) and (b) amplitude and phase for the Approach Mach number and zero flow incidence. (c) and (d) for Landing for Mach number and flow incidence.

Figure 16 shows the uncorrelated noise levels for the cut-on dominant mode in the rig VT4-1 (left) and the modified rig VT4-3 (right). The figure shows two of the five working lines tested, with all the conditions measured and three conditions of each working line simulated numerically. The agreement between measurements and numerical

predictions is consistent with the precision observed in LPTs, with a maximum discrepancy of 3dB for certain conditions. It is interesting to remark that the comparison between VT4-1 and VT4-3 shows similar uncorrelated noise levels in the two rigs, the optimized vane shape in NGV2 of rig VT4-3 does not provoke a clear noise increase or decrease compared with rig VT4-1, being the discrepancy between both included in the uncertainty of the experiment.

Figure 16. VT4-1 (left) and VT4-3 (right) measured vs predicted uncorrelated noise levels.

The number-off coincidence between both NGV rows makes that the noise generated by the interaction with the rotor is coherent and depends on the relative circumferential position between NGV1 and NGV2. Noise measured for the cut-on dominant mode at different positions is represented in **Figure 17** for two conditions of the 32 tested, corresponding to 60% nominal reduced shaft speed and two different loadings. Both rigs, VT4-1 and modified VT4-3 are shown on the left and right, respectively.

Figure 17. VT4-1 (left) and VT4-3 (right) measured vs predicted uncorrelated noise levels.

With regard to VT4-1, **Figure 17**-left shows different clocking sensitivity for the two conditions. There is agreement in this subject between numerical predictions and measurements, although a discrepancy in the optimum clocking position for noise is observed in the numerical prediction. Again, prediction capability for clocking sensitivity is aligned with previous experiments for LPTs [6][22]. With the objective of increasing the potential benefit of the clocking technology, VT4-1 was re-designed in VT4-3 with an optimized vane shape in NGV2. Figure 17 (right)

shows the same two conditions numerically predicted and measured in this rig, with consistency between both in terms of uncorrelated level, clocking sensitivity and optimum position for noise. The benefit of having an optimized vane shape to power the acoustic coupling is clearly visible from Figure 17, in consistency with the numerical study presented in Serrano et. al [22].

VII. Conclusion

The capability of the linear CFD code Mu²s²-L to predicted tonal noise in HSTs has been verified with numerical predictions of 1.5-stage rigs representative of the forward and rear part of a HST. Aerodynamic and noise measured data of these rigs is available and have been used to conclude regarding the fidelity to estimate wake amplitudes, uncorrelated tone noise levels and clocking sensitivities.

The first rig used is representative of the forward part of the turbine, showing the ability of the CFD to predict high order wake harmonics of a low aspect ratio and low number-off vane. The mechanisms that generate noise are well identified and show similar predicted levels to the measurements. Due to the number-off relation between the NGV rows, there exist a clocking sensitivity with the relative position between them, which is captured by the CFD in terms of uncorrelated noise level and clocking delta. The measured radial content is not fully explained by the numerical model, with discrepancies in certain circumferential modes. The optimum clocking position is predicted with a mean deviation of 15% respect the measurements.

The second comparison performed in this work uses measured results coming from a rig representative of the rear part of a HST, which have coincident number-off in the stationary rows NGV1 and NGV2. Wake harmonic intensities estimated are consistent with measurements coming from different fast response probes. The uncorrelated noise level for the dominant cut-on mode is estimated including the multiple transmission along the turbine, showing coherence with the measured level. The clocking phenomena is also investigated raising similar conclusions to previous works in LPTs, with coherent clocking sensitivities and mean discrepancies in the optimum clocking position of 15% pitch. The numerical simulation of this rig includes also the re-design of the NGV2 with an optimized shape to increase clocking sensitivity. The experimentally measured increase in the clocking benefit when this vane is introduced is also captured numerically.

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